

The Labyrinth in Landscape Design

Kadirov Elshod Baxtiyor o`g`li¹

¹Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering University, Uzbekistan, Samarkand

Abstract:

Today there are styles of garden design. But among all areas of landscape design two most popular ones can be distinguished: regular and landscape style. A harmonical combination of individual elements of styles to create a unique of the landscape. In this article I want to show the way to combine the labyrinth and of weaving branches.

Keywords: the labyrinth, Feng-Shui experts, landscape design.

Introduction. Having historical, cultural, and religious roots, humans have been walking the path of the labyrinth for centuries. From seashores to cathedral floors, the labyrinth is seen as a symbolic search for one's center. The labyrinth has experienced a revival in modern life, showing up everywhere from rehabilitation centers and hospitals, to prisons and backyard landscapes across this country.

The labyrinth has emerged as a form that can help humans find their internal center and place of emotional stability. A labyrinth is a special place in the park where thick plants are grown to make confusing and irregular paths. As it is written in the Encyclopaedia, according to the dictionary of symbols, a labyrinth is a metaphor of a human's lifetime journey. In terms of technology, a labyrinth has several paths, which lead to the centre with difficult structures of passage. Most labyrinths are created with a classic design, using Romanstone brick or limestone. Bricks are recessed into the ground to delineate a walking path for visitors. The ground is graded to remediate soil and provide for slight drainage away from the center of the labyrinth promoting ideal, long-term site conditions.

2. Methodology. Looking back at history, the image of the first labyrinths is found in the colour pictures on the stones all over the world. Ancient people believed that they could save their houses from evil spirits by misleading them to the labyrinth. Nowadays, Feng-Shui experts consider that the properly created labyrinth serves as a redirector of the energy protection. In the art of the European landscape, it was tradition to create a labyrinth in gardens of castles and in natural parks. To promenade in the labyrinth was a favourite activity of the noblemen and the noblewomen. Today also, a labyrinth is an element, which is widely used in the landscape design. A labyrinth may be either big or small, either complicated or simple, and may constitute different plants, like flowers, different stones, paths and others. The labyrinth's size, the extent of confusion and the constitution of the source are not as important

as the correctly selected image of it. A labyrinth can be located in children's areas or in leisure parks. A labyrinth is like a magnet for children, it attracts them, as it is a convenient place for them to play 'hide-and-seek' and run after each other. While, for adults it serves as a place to promenade and to contemplate. If you want to create a labyrinth in your own area, first of all, you will need to allocate a field for it, and to measure the width of the field. Any labyrinth can be in an optional

height, the convenience of watching it from above, to have a better view of the labyrinth, must be taken into consideration. There are two types of labyrinths. The simplest type of a labyrinth is the winding spiral labyrinth (or two crossing spirals). And a complicated type of labyrinth (a.k.a. a maze) consists of entanglements, and deadend. A corridors, as well as several paths, leading to different entrances. In the labyrinth project the importance of the centre area is indispensable, because there must be a purpose to overcome the confusing paths. It is most desired if there is a terrace for refreshment, or there are benches surrounded by flowers in the centre. Flower beds, sculptures, small fountains, sundials, composition of forms that portrays different animals or fruits made of flexible bushes can serve as the centre of the labyrinth.

Nowadays, invented shapes in the field of landscaping amazes any man with their originality. These kinds of shapes can be used in gardens and parks as well. It is even more amazing to use them for the labyrinth. Just imagine: you are walking through the labyrinth heading to its centre, when you reach the centre you will find in front of you a huge shape of a lion or an apple made of bushes... Certainly, you feel that it is created by a human, and as if you are in an amazing world in a fairytale. And

during the labyrinth it seems as if there are wonders of a magical country waiting ahead. To conclude, taking into consideration the size of the land, resources and general composition of solutions, maintains the level of the perfect artwork when any labyrinth is created.

3. Results and Discussion. The labyrinth as it engages the individual creates a shift from the

‘ordinary’ to the ‘extraordinary’ in terms of experience. It effects consciousness, through the senses. It structures the space it occupies. Landscape architecture is a field that can design and construct this object, and create environments to heighten or enhance the experience of this object. It is important to recognize that landscape architecture necessarily has an impact upon the environment and the people within it. It is a field where innovation is looked upon favorably, as the ultimate goal as a professional is to create safe, pleasing outdoor environments for people. As a future landscape architect, I inherently

believe in creating conscious and thoughtful design innovations and interventions that enhance the quality of life for humans. Landscape architecture can play a role in the creation of these environments beyond the normal cosmetic response or manipulation of physical space. While the labyrinth is just one of the environments in which this can happen, it is an intriguing and mysterious quest.

Conclusion. Having walked the labyrinth and believing in its healing properties, I became interested in the symbol itself. I was intrigued by the way the symbol was actually an architectural element that told the narrative of the culture that built it. While the labyrinth was on church floors in medieval times, its revival in modern times seems to be located in the outdoor environment. Since Landscape Architecture is a field based on the creation of safe and pleasing outdoor environments for humans, I chose the labyrinth as a way of looking at "experience" and "contemplation" in the landscape, and how the design (the creation of form) of this object contributes to the analysis.

References:

1. Все о дизайне сада. Элементы ландшафта. Лабиринт в саду. pro-landshaft.ru – 2009 2016
2. Статья Юлии Фомина из журнала “Цветы” на тему “Скульптуры украшения сада” –07. 2002
3. Ландшафтный дизайн. Скульптуры. Плетенные скульптуры в саду – на модной волне. фото 7dach.ru ООО «7дач» – 127018, г.Москва, ул. Полковая,